

Famen Monastery 法門寺

also known as “Aśoka Monastery”, “Chengshi Monastery 成實寺”, “Ayuwang Monastery 阿育王寺”, “Chongzhen Monastery 重真寺”

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Entry tags: Pagoda, Religious Group, China, Chinese Buddhism, Monastery, Religious Place, Chinese Religion, Religious Complex

Famen Monastery 法門寺 was an important center of imperial cult during the Tang dynasty. A Fufeng area 扶風 (northwest of modern-day Xi'an) gazetteer dates the foundation of the so-called Aśoka Monastery to the year 67 CE, when one of the Buddha's finger bones was supposedly interred in that area. Excavated Han dynasty tiles have also led some to corroborate the theory that this presumed first iteration of Famen Monastery was indeed founded in the first century. In c. 555 CE, a Northern Wei general would have translated the finger bone to its location at the newly established Famen Monastery. However, by the seventh century the site was in ruins as a result of the anti-Buddhist policies enacted during the Northern Zhou persecution of Buddhism (574-577). The Buddhist historian Daoxuan 道宣 (596-667) noted that a new monastery and pagoda structure was erected by Emperor Wen (r. 581-604) of the Sui dynasty near a place called Phoenix Spring, south of Mount Qi 岐山. At that time, Emperor Wen conferred the name Chengshi Monastery 成實寺 on this complex. The monastery once again fell into disrepair until the year 618 when monks from nearby Baochang Monastery 寶昌寺 petitioned the newly crowned Tang Emperor Gaozu for support in re-establishing Famen. However, as the Tang established control over the territory, Famen was most likely used as a fortified garrison against brigands and was destroyed. It was not until 632 under Emperor Taizong that it was properly renovated, at which point multiple relics including the revered finger bone of the Buddha were discovered within the pagoda's foundations on the monastery grounds. A prophecy discovered at that time stated that every thirty years miraculous events would occur and the relic would need once more to be taken out and presented to the people. Indeed, during the Tang dynasty the finger bone was translated to the capitals of Chang'an and Luoyang six times: in 660, 704, 760, 790, 819, and for the last time in 873. The pagoda containing the finger bone constructed during the Tang, also known as the True Body pagoda, stood tall until 1596. The octagonal pagoda built to replace it in 1609 stood thirteen stories tall and remained intact until 1981 when it crumbled after heavy rainfall. In 1987, six years after the True Body pagoda crumbled, the Famen complex was excavated leading to the discovery of a treasure trove of cultural artifacts dating back to the Han through to the Ming dynasty. Of particular importance was the Tang dynasty Famen pagoda crypt last sealed in 874, which had escaped the attention of looters and remained perfectly intact. The same is regrettably not true of the Ming dynasty crypt above it. There is today in Fufeng county a very modern reconstruction of Famen Monastery which sits at the epicenter of a 150 acre park called the "Famen Temple Cultural Scenic Area". The monastery still claims to hold one of the Tang's most revered Buddhist relics which was discovered by archeologists in 1987: the Buddha's finger bone.

Date Range: 67 CE - 960 CE

Region: Fufeng County outside of Xi'an, Shaanxi Province

Region tags: China, Chang'an (Xi'an), Yellow and Yangzi Rivers Region

Famen Monastery was in Fufeng 扶風 district outside of Chang'an, present-day Xi'an. It was said to be south of Mount Qi 岐山 near a place called Phoenix Springs.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Han Jinke. Famen si wenhua yanjiu: lishi juan 法門寺文化研究: 歷史卷. Vol. 4. Famen si wenhua congshu 法門寺文化叢書. Xi'an: Shaanxi sheng famen si bowu guan, 1993.
- Source 2: Han Jinke. Famen si 法門寺. Beijing: Wuzhou chuanbo chuban she, 1998.
- Source 3: Whitfield, Roderick. 'Discoveries from the Famen Monastery at Fufeng and the Qingshan Monastery at Lintong, Shaanxi Province'. In *The Golden Age of Chinese Archaeology: Celebrated Discoveries from the People's Republic of China*: Ed. by Xiaoneng Yang; [Exhibition Organized by] National Gallery of Art, Washington, The Nelson Atkins Museum of Art, Kansas City., edited by Xiaoneng Yang, 463–87. New Haven: Yale University Press, 1999.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.encyclopedia.com/religion/encyclopedias-almanacs-transcripts-and-maps/famensi>
- Source 1 Description: Basic introduction.
- Source 2 URL: <http://www.fmsjq.com/>
- Source 2 Description: The Famen website in mainland China.

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Notes: After heavy rainfall in 1981, the western side of the Famen Monastery pagoda collapsed. The site was made safe in 1985, though it was not until April 3rd 1987 that the excavation work began in earnest.

Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1987

Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: Excavation of the pagoda's "foundation deposit"

Notes: Many pagodas in China are built with a "foundation deposit", or a crypt. The Famen pagoda was no exception.

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Water source

– Other [specify]: Mountain

Notes: Famen Monastery's location had an auspicious past going all the way back to the Zhou dynasty (1050-771 BCE). The revered Zhou ancestor Gu Gong Dan Fu 古公亶父 (Ancient Patriarch Father Dan) crossed the Ju and the Qi rivers to found Qizhou 岐周 in the Zhou plain south of Mount Qi 岐山. This location was particularly auspicious because it was popularly believed that the Phoenix Springs nearby had once been visited by a phoenix, a good omen as well as a symbol of regal authority and prestige. This young phoenix appears in the Guo Yu 國語: "At the height of the Zhou dynasty, the young phoenix cried out in the Qishan range" (1.10 f.).

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Type of feature

– Leveling of ground

– Terracing

– Clearing

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Notes: It was about 30 miles away from the Tang capital of Chang'an, making Famen Monastery accessible to people living in this thriving urban center.

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Notes: There was a garrison nearby as well as some villages.

Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Notes: This monastery was used for some imperially mandated ceremonies. Its relative proximity to the capital was central to its support and success.

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– No

↳ One single feature

– Clearing

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– Yes

Notes: In the style of other medieval Chinese wards and secular compounds, Buddhist monastic complexes included peripheral structures and a courtyard giving access to all the halls. Indeed, the layout of the lecture halls, Sutra halls, meditation halls, pagodas, and more were arrayed across the ward in the fashion of an imperial compound. Active Chinese monasteries served a variety of different secular purposes as well, acting not only as centers of Buddhist learning and ritual practice, but also as granaries, orphanages, treasuries, and much more

↳ A group of features:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– Yes

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

Notes: The monastic complex contained various halls, residences, and sometimes multiple pagodas.

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

Notes: The various halls were communal spaces used for prayer and study. Some of these halls were reserved for those monastics living in the complex. Other halls were open to the public, and lectures or ceremonies were carried out there.

– Memorial

Notes: By the Tang dynasty, every monastery also included a pagoda. This pagoda might contain Buddha relics, or might be erected to memorialize eminent monks or other such figures.

– Political

Notes: Famen Monastery was an officially mandated complex. The various renovations carried out there throughout its history were funded by members of the ruling class. The finger bone relic contained within its main pagoda was also very important to the ruling family. There was therefore a political dimension to many of the structures and features at Famen.

– Other [specify]: Housing

Notes: Monks lived at Famen, constituting a coherent religious community with a certain degree of independence from secular society.

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

Notes: Famen Monastery has been renovated multiple times throughout the course of history. It was reconstructed during the Sui dynasty, and on multiple occasions throughout the Tang. Its final iteration in imperial history was in 1579 when they constructed a massive octagonal tower that was thirteen stories tall. Since the pagoda's collapse in 1981, it as well as the monastery have been reconstructed. During the 2000s, the monastic grounds were expanded and turned into a large park with Famen

Monastery at its epicenter.

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

– Collapsed

Notes: It was first destroyed during the Zhou extirpation of Buddhism (574-577). It was later rebuilt during the Sui dynasty and then again in the Tang. Since then it has been rebuilt multiple times. The penultimate version of the pagoda was an ambitious Ming dynasty octagonal construction out of brick. The structure was so large that it crushed its own foundations as it slowly began leaning towards the west. In 1981, after earthquakes and heavy rainfall, the pagoda collapsed once more. A new pagoda and monastery complex has since been erected.

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

– For religious reasons

– For political reasons

Notes: Famen Monastery was targeted by the anti-Buddhist policies of the Northern Zhou. Although it may not have been razed to the ground by troops, the community there was scattered and the monastery grounds were left uncared for.

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:

– Natural phenomena

Notes: In most instances, the monastery structures simply degraded after years of neglect. When the pagoda crumbled in 1981, it was the result of a recent earthquake followed by very heavy rainfall.

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Yes

↳ In antiquity

– More than once

Notes: If we date the first iteration of Famen to the Eastern Han, we could say it was first reconstructed in 558. It was reconstructed later in the sixth century under Emperor Wen, in 632 under Taizong, again in 1609 during the Ming dynasty, and for a last time in our modern era during the 1980s.

↳ In modernity

– Renaissance

– Post-Renaissance

Notes: If we date the first iteration of Famen to the Eastern Han, we could say it was first reconstructed in 558. It was again reconstructed later in the sixth century under Emperor Wen, in 632 under Taizong, again in 1609 during the Ming dynasty, and for a last time in our modern era during the 1980s.

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Buddha

Notes: The pagoda in particular was said to contain the Buddha's finger bone. Ontologically, relics imply the 'presence' of the saints—they are the saints, just as the portrait of Caesar is said to actually be Caesar. Relics are the 'living' remain of a saint, establishing its place as the axial point of merit-making ideology. As vital and living entities, relics possess what Jennifer S. Hughes refers to as 'agentic potency' because they have the power to affect 'social relations, behaviours, and outcomes', not to mention other lifelike qualities attributed to relics such as moving at will, flying, shaking, walking, bouncing, and more. As a sacred marker and as a vessel for the finger bone, the Famen pagoda was revered by many as synecdochical representation of the Buddha—the Buddha not in flesh and blood but in brick and mortar.

Reference: Hughes, Jennifer. "Mysterium Materiae: Vital Matter and the Object as Evidence in the Study of Religion". *Bulletin for the Study of Religion* 41, no. 4 (January 1, 2012). p.16-24

Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

Notes: Although other supernormal beings might be active at the monastery and within the pagoda, these were not dedicated to them.

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

↳ Specify

– King or emperor

Notes: Every new renovation of Famen Monastery was funded by the ruling family. For example, the second Famen Monastery was supported by Emperor Wen of the Sui. Later, after the triumphant Tang took power, Emperor Gaozu rewarded the community at Famen for its support during the civil war by beginning renovations on the complex. It was again renovated in 632 by Emperor Taizong. Throughout Chinese history, the norm was for large imperially mandated monasteries to receive patronage from the ruling elite.

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– No

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Yes

Notes: Famen Monastery was believed to be founded on the vestiges of an Aśokan site. Legend tells that King Aśoka (c. 268–c. 232 BCE), the great Buddhist king of India, ordered that spirits distribute the Buddha's relics and erect pagodas to mark their place across the globe. Inheriting this Indian legend, the Chinese attributed 'Aśokan' origins to many sites and objects as a means of legitimizing their authenticity and to underline their importance. Famen Monastery was such a place, and was thus also known as Aśoka Monastery. The community and its patrons were mindful of this fact when they constructed and renovated the site. The Aśokan association brought prestige and gravitas to the site.

↳ Specify

– Prophecy

Notes: Famen Monastery was believed to be founded on the vestiges of an Aśokan site. Legend tells that King Aśoka (c. 268–c. 232 BCE), the great Buddhist king of India, ordered that spirits distribute the Buddha's relics and erect pagodas to mark their place across the globe. Inheriting this Indian legend, the Chinese attributed 'Aśokan' origins to many sites and objects as a means of legitimizing their authenticity and to underline their importance. Famen Monastery was such a place, and was thus also known as Aśoka Monastery. The community and its patrons were mindful of this fact when they constructed and renovated the site. The Aśokan association brought prestige and gravitas to the site.

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Yes

↳ Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

– No

Notes: Famen was supposedly founded in the mid-sixth century. The sponsor was almost certainly the Western Wei rulers, who perhaps were sympathetic to Buddhism but were certainly not piously Buddhist. In medieval China, imperial patronage of religious institutions was usually politically motivated. Although Emperor Wen of the Sui was himself quite interested in Buddhism, this was certainly not the case for his successors during the Tang, whose support of Famen was usually politically motivated. Supporting Buddhism helped rulers curry favor with the people and also helped integrate these religious communities into the larger state apparatus.

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expectation of favor in return

Notes: It is unclear exactly what the motivations were for establishing Famen. Everything we know about it relies on what the excavated artifacts can tell us, and what Tang as well as later historian-monks wrote about Famen. Monastery building projects were usually associated to merit-making activity in medieval Chinese Buddhism, and this most likely was the motivation for founding Famen. In Buddhism, accruing merit does not necessarily have any immediate benefits, though it was believed to help one and their family members in the afterlife and in their next lives.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Notes: From the seventh century onward, Famen Monastery certainly would have had a structures such as a 'sutra hall' 經堂 for collecting and preserving scriptures, though this was not the primary motivation for building the monastery.

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– No

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

Notes: Famen Monastery was a compound with surrounding buildings, a courtyard, a pagoda, and various central halls. Many of these structures would have been attached.

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Notes: The main Buddha hall and the pagoda containing the Buddha's finger bone would have been the most important structures at Famen.

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:

– Field doesn't know

Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is unclear just how large the Famen pagoda was at any time. We know that when it was rebuilt during the Ming, the new pagoda had an octagonal design and was thirteen stories tall. A second modern pagoda, called Namaste Dagoba, was designed by a Taiwanese architect and covers an area of 40,500 square meters.

Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It is unclear how tall the pagoda would have been during medieval times. During the Ming, the main pagoda, also known as the True Body pagoda 真身塔, was built thirteen stories high, approximately 43 meters tall. The tallest structure at Famen Monastery today is the Namaste Pagoda, that stands 148 meters tall.

Size of average monument, square meters:

– I don't know

Height of average monument, meters:

– I don't know

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

Earth

– No

↳ Sand

– No

↳ Clay

– Field doesn't know

↳ Plaster

– Field doesn't know

↳ Wood

– Yes

Notes: Wood was the primary building material in medieval China. In the monastery, it was used for the halls, the residences, and all other structures. Wood was also used in the pagoda's structures.

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Grass

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

Notes: Nowhere in the medieval sources do they describe the building materials used in the early Famen Monastery constructions. According to descriptions of other monasteries and pagodas in the textual sources, we know that they used stone for the foundations. They often used layered bricks for the pagoda structures, while most of the other structures would be made out of wood.

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Brick

Notes: Although we cannot say for certain that the first iterations of the Famen True Body pagoda were made of brick, the Chinese certainly had the technology and literary evidence would indicate that similar pagoda from that time were made out of brick.

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: Brick

Notes: Although we cannot say for certain that the first iterations of the Famen True Body pagoda were made of brick, the Chinese certainly had the technology and literary evidence would indicate that similar pagodas from that time were made out of brick.

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

Notes: Although none of the original structures have survived, we can assume that Famen Monastery would have been like any other imperially mandated monastery during the Tang, and that it would be decorated accordingly.

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

Notes: Although we have very few details about Famen Monastery as it was during the medieval period, the Tang architectural style was both practical and decorative. Monastery buildings as well as pagodas included ornate bracketing and the roofs traditionally had flying eaves. Roderick Whitfield claims that one the gilt bronze votive stupa containing the Buddha finger bone discovered in the first crypt gives us an idea of the High Tang architectural style [p. 468]. The votive pagoda has a tiled roof with flying eaves, and it is adorned on top with a spire adorned by rings.

Reference: Shaanxi Provincial Institute of Archeology 陕西省考古研究所. Famen Shanxi Sheng Kaogu Yanjiusuokaogu Fajue Baogao 法门寺考古发掘报告. Vol. 1. Wenwu chubanshe 文物出版社, 2007.

Reference: Han, Sheng. Famensi Wenwu Tubu 法门寺文物图饰. Wenwu chubanshe, 2009.

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

Notes: Famen would certainly have been decorated on the inside. Banners would have adorned the walls, images of the Buddha and of bodhisattvas would have been occupied a central place in most structures. No details are given anywhere about the distribution of decorative elements in the halls, but we know for certain based on Famen's position viz a viz the state that it would have been lavishly decorated. Pictures of the famen crypts show that the small doors were adorned with painted or relief arches, and that images of bodhisattvas and the Buddha were present both in the form of statues and as paintings on the wall.

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

Notes: Aside from permanent decorative elements such as intricate bracketing and flying eaves, monasteries and other structures were usually adorned with movable decorations. Writing about another state supported monastery in the early ninth century, Bai Juyi 白居易 praised the newly renovated Kaiyuan Monastery, noting the size of the complex, made up of several hundred buildings, as well as the star-shaped decorations adorning all the buildings [Sokolova 2021, 12]. Moreover, as attested to by discoveries in the Dunhuang caves, banners and tapestries were also a common form of adornment in monasteries. We do not know what Famen Monastery would have looked like at the time, but as an imperially mandated monastery, Famen would certainly have been decorated appropriately.

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– I don't know

Notes: The deities of Buddhism are part of the iconography present in almost all monasteries, though we do not know for certain whether they were depicted on the structures at Famen during the medieval period. However, gods are depicted on the objects kept in the Famen pagoda crypts. For example, many precious containers used to hold the relics at Famen included images of gods. Although these containers and their relics were mostly kept hidden, only appearing during processions, the gods depicted on the containers would certainly also have appeared on the other decorations at Famen. I have also attached an image of two door gods 門神, probably the divinized Tang generals Qin Shubao and Yu Chigong, that were painted onto a locked door in the Famen pagoda Tang dynasty crypt.

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Depictions of the Buddha and bodhisattvas in many mediums would certainly

have been present at Famen. Perhaps one of the most famous ritual objects was the True Body bodhisattva image. This image holds up a platter that may have held the finger bone relic during Tang dynasty processions. Although people probably only saw this image during the processions, which happened about every thirty years, this bodhisattva was one of many such images that would have been present at the Famen monastic complex.

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Daoxuan 道宣 writes in his *Ji shenzhou sanbao gantong lu* 集神州三寶感通錄 about the production of an image in the likeness of King Aśoka, paragon of Buddhist rule, donated by Emperor Gaozong for the monastery. This image in particular is interesting because Daoxuan notes that Gaozong ordered that this statue be made according to his own dimensions, essentially equating his royal self to the renowned Mauryan monarch. This image is no longer extant. There were also carved into the walls of the front room in the Famen pagoda crypt, images of monks doing obeisance at Famen.

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Many different animals would have been depicted on the walls and arches at Famen. The attached image presents an arch relief of two phoenixes facing one another. Mythical animals such as the phoenix and the dragon were considered auspicious beings and had strong imperial associations. Other animals would certainly also have been depicted in the monastery and on other outlying structures.

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– I don't know

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

Notes: There would have been many different geometric patterns painted or carved onto wood or stone. I have attached an image of the crypt where the arch presents a painted clover-like pattern.

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

Notes: There would have been many different geometric and floral patterns painted or carved onto wood or stone. I have attached an image of the crypt where the arch presents a painted clover-like pattern.

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– Yes

Notes: There would have been banners and boards with scriptural passages used to decorate the monastic complex.

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: No

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– Yes

↳ Can the decoration be revealed:

– Yes

Notes: Not all decorations were hidden from view. However, many of the donations and artworks dedicated to the finger relic were kept hidden in a crypt beneath the foundations of Famen pagoda. There was in the rear chamber a staff and other precious objects. In the hidden niche beneath the rear chamber they found a finger bone relic. Objects such as the finger bone were ritually revealed every thirty years or so in large and vibrant processions that sometimes went as far as the eastern capital of Luoyang.

↳ Are there statues present:

– Yes

↳ Cult statues:

– Yes

Notes: Many of the statues discovered in the crypt at Famen pagoda were important objects of cult. The True Body bodhisattva depicted below was a cult object that was probably used to hold the relic during the relic procession.

↳ Statues of gods/supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: Many of the statues that remain today date back to the Ming dynasty. They depict the Buddha, usually sitting cross-legged on a lotus platform. Textual evidence would indicate that there would have been other images in the crypt before the Ming. Buddha and bodhisattva statues would also have been prevalent in every monastery structure.

↳ Statues of humans:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Lions

Notes: Lions, traditionally in pairs, are placed on both sides of a door to act as guards.

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– Yes

Notes: This 'yes' comes with a short caveat. Buddha's and bodhisattvas were considered god-like, but they were not gods in the same way as in Hinduism or in the Abrahamic traditions. Buddha's and bodhisattvas are beings of this world that can operate at a level beyond this worldly realm because of their understanding of the processual and conditional nature of all things. Therefore, they are not 'gods' but supernatural beings with a god-like understanding of all things.

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

– Yes

Notes: Four versions of the fingerbone relic were discovered in the Famen crypt, though all but one were consider replicas, or "shadow relics" 影骨. Each replica was preserved in a suite of decorated cases, many of which had lavish decorations such as encrusted pearls or intricate depictions made in relief on the metal. It is on one of these cases that we find an example of a relief representing a mythological narrative. There was an eight container set, of which the fifth largest contained various mythological scenes in Buddhist lore. Among other things, the container depicted an Amitabha Buddha paradise scene and the Buddha preaching. There may well have been other reliefs depicting similar scenes, though such reliefs were either looted in the 1980's or have simply been destroyed.

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

– I don't know

Notes: Historical narratives do appear in Buddhist artistic depictions. For example, cave 323 at Dunhuang has many such narratives related to Buddhism. However, I do not know if such narratives were depicted at Famen.

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: No

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– Yes

Notes: To give one example, there were paintings of door gods which were painted on movable panels that were then used as doors. These gods appear on all the door leading to the inner sanctum of the Famen pagoda crypt.

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– Yes

↳ Type

–Secco

Notes: We only have paintings remaining from the crypt. Here we only have examples of paintings done on panels and patterns painted on dry plaster. Still, wall painting was a popular practice in medieval China and it is safe to assume that they would have had wall paintings at Famen.

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– Yes

Notes: We only have paintings remaining from the crypt. Here we only have examples of paintings done on panels and patterns painted on dry plaster. These represent door guards or floral patterns. Still, wall painting was a popular practice in medieval China and it is safe to assume that they would have had wall paintings of the Buddha and of bodhisattvas at Famen.

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– I don't know

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– I don't know

Notes: Historical narratives do appear in Buddhist artistic depictions. For example, cave 323 at Dunhuang has many such narratives related to Buddhism painted onto the walls. However, I do not know if such narratives were depicted at Famen.

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: No

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– I don't know

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– Yes

Notes: There would have been ornamental steles on the monastic grounds.

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative

[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

Notes: Famen Monastery contained many steles and other such inscriptions describing events at the monastery. Most famous among these are the steles recounting events related to the relic processions that took place throughout the Tang. For example, there was the "Famen Huigong Dade stele 法門惠恭大德之碑" inscribed in 689, which described the monk Huigong's life, the immolation of two of his fingers as an offering to the finger bone relic, as well as his role in the finger relic cult out of the capital [Han Sheng p.23]. There is also evidence in the Famen pagoda crypt that officials participating in the relic procession inscribed their names on the wall of the crypt. They simply list their names and note that they participated in the relic procession.

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– Yes

Notes: Many dedication inscriptions were discovered in the crypt beneath Famen pagoda. Famen Monastery was an imperially mandated monastery, and the finger bone procession was a parade of both religious and political importance. Officials participating in the procession sometimes signed their names in the crypt as both a merit making act and as proof of attendance. There were moreover tablets kept deep in the crypt recording the donated goods and the names of those that donated, usually members of the ruling class.

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: No

↳ Other type of decoration:

– No

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: There are not many zoomorphic representations of supernatural beings, though we note on the container for one of the copies of the finger bone relic, there is a depiction of a half-bird half-human, probably a kalaviṅka of the Western pure land.

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– Yes

Notes: The pagoda itself is an abstract, even aniconic, representation of the Buddha. In India, the pagoda (Skt. stūpa) was believed to invoke the presence of the Buddha--a belief that was transmitted east to China. After the Buddha passed away, legend tells that his remains were preserved as holy relics and placed in pagodas. As the vessels for these relics, pagodas were believed to represent the Buddha. They were believed to imply his very presence not in flesh and blood but in mortar and stone. Indian pagodas followed strict symbolic guidelines so that everything from the rounded mound to the top of the spire carried set symbolic meaning. Pagodas and smaller votive pagodas in China did not necessarily hold the same symbolic importance. Indeed, there were instances where pagodas served not only a religious function, but geomantic functions as well. However, in the minds of the medieval Chinese, the pagoda continued to represent the Buddha.

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Although it is not uncommon to see depictions of the Buddhist hells in wall paintings, no such representations were found in the Famen pagoda crypt. Therefore, we cannot say for certain whether the afterlife was portrayed at Famen.

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– Yes

Notes: The most studied iconographic aspects of doctrine studied in relation to Famen are the esoteric Buddhist symbols found in the Tang crypt. Esoteric, or Vajrayana, Buddhist practice and thought was brought to China from India and Central Asia by tantric masters and translators such as Śubhakarasiṃha and Amoghavajra. They brought with them a new ritual technology which we can today find among the cultural artifacts in the Tang crypt. This is

especially true of the forty-five-deity relic bone case which was decorated with representations inspired by Tantric Mandalas (see in the images below). Another example is the famous image of a bodhisattva kneeling on a lotus-shaped dais (inscribed in 871), which has images on its pedestal drawing from the Vajradhatu Mandala, the most prevalent esoteric iconography at Famen (see below). For more on this topic, the reader may refer to an article by Sharf 2011. The most prevalent esoteric aspect of doctrine is the vajra, a five-pronged short club that represents Buddhist enlightenment and indestructibility.

Reference: Sharf, Robert. "The Buddha's Finger Bones at Fameni and the Art of Chinese Esoteric Buddhism". *The Art Bulletin* 93, no. 1 (January 1, 2011). p.38-59

↳ Humans

– Yes

Notes: One example of iconography representing humans in the Famen script is inscribed on the floor of the front room in the Tang Famen crypt. The inscriptions present multiple individual monks kneeling and doing obeisance to the finger bone relic. Each monk is presented in full robes with their names and monastic affiliation inscribed to their left.

↳ Supernatural narratives

– Yes

Notes: Four versions of the fingerbone relic were discovered in the Famen crypt, though all but one were considered replicas, or "shadow relics" 影骨. Each replica was preserved in a suite of decorated cases, many of which had lavish decorations such as encrusted pearls or intricate depictions made in relief on the metal. It is on one of these cases that we find an example of a relief representing supernatural narratives. There was an eight container set, of which the fifth largest contained various supernatural scenes. Among other things, the container depicted an Amitabha Buddha paradise scene and the Buddha preaching. There may well have been other reliefs depicting similar scenes, though such reliefs were either looted in the 1980's or have simply been destroyed.

↳ Human narratives

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: No

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: According to the Nirvana Sutra, when the Buddha passed away, vying kingdom fought for possession of his remains. The Brahmin Drona brokered a deal between these competing kingdoms,

avoiding the looming 'war of the relics', which stipulated that the Buddha's remains be split into eight parts to be distributed to each kingdom. These were then placed in so-called pagodas (Skt. stūpas), rounded dome structures inspired by traditional Indian funerary mounds. However, historically the pagoda represented more than just a funerary mound. As a vessel for the Buddha's relics, it was believed to embody the Buddha's 'presence' in this worldly realm--the Buddha in mortar and stone. Pagodas in medieval China were traditionally erected to commemorate the establishment of a monastery, the translation of a sacred cult object (e.g. a relic of the Buddha, a miraculous image) to the new monastery, the life of an eminent Buddhist figure, and more. Tracy Miller writes that certain translators in seventh century China compared the pagoda (ta 塔) with the Tang dynasty tumulus (fen 墳), where the remains of deceased members of the gentry class were ceremonially buried. She notes that while there is a consensus in the field of South Asian studies regarding the relationship between early Indian funerary mounds and the Buddhist pagoda, the latter is not, strictly speaking, a tomb because not all remains warranted burial in a pagoda, and because the pagoda itself was a sacred structure implying the Buddha's presence, or the life and presence of whatever other saint that the pagoda commemorated. This was also true in China, where there was perhaps an association between the pagoda and the royal tumulus, but no direct equivalence [Miller 2018, p. 92]. If we take the example of Xuanzang's reliquary pagoda in Xi'an which was erected after his death in the mid-seventh century, although some of his remains may be interred in the pagoda's foundations, the structure itself is not a tomb but a commemorative monument and an empowered religious structure. Bearing this in mind, the Famen pagoda which contains the Buddha's finger bone was not considered a tomb but a sacred place made holy by its illustrious history and the potent relics and religious objects it contained.

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– Yes

For the worship of a deceased person(s):

– Yes

Notes: According to the Nirvana Sutra, when the Buddha passed away, vying kingdom fought for possession of his remains. The Brahmin Drona brokered a deal between these competing kingdoms, avoiding the looming 'war of the relics', which stipulated that the Buddha's remains be split into eight parts to be distributed to each kingdom. These were then placed in so-called pagodas (Skt. stūpas), rounded dome structures inspired by traditional Indian funerary mounds. However, historically the pagoda represented more than just a funerary mound. As a vessel for the Buddha's relics, it was believed to embody the Buddha's 'presence' in this worldly realm--the Buddha in mortar and stone. Pagodas in medieval China were traditionally erected to commemorate the establishment of a monastery, the translation of a sacred cult object (e.g. a relic of the Buddha, a miraculous image) to the new monastery, the life of an eminent Buddhist figure, and more. Tracy Miller writes that certain translators in seventh century China compared the pagoda (ta 塔) with the Tang dynasty tumulus (fen 墳), where the remains of deceased members of the gentry class were ceremonially buried. She notes that while there is a consensus in the field of South Asian studies regarding the relationship between early Indian funerary mounds and the Buddhist pagoda, the latter is not, strictly speaking, a tomb because not all remains warranted burial in a pagoda, and because the pagoda itself was a sacred structure implying the Buddha's presence, or the life and presence of whatever other saint that the pagoda commemorated. This was also true in China, where there was perhaps an association between the pagoda and the royal tumulus, but no direct equivalence [Miller 2018, p. 92]. If we take the example of Xuanzang's reliquary pagoda in Xi'an which was erected after his death in the mid-seventh century, although some of his remains may be interred in the pagoda's foundations, the structure itself is not a tomb but a commemorative monument and

an empowered religious structure. Bearing this in mind, the Famen pagoda which contains the Buddha's finger bone was not considered a tomb but a sacred place made holy by its illustrious history and the potent relics and religious objects it contained.

↳ For the worship of a deified human:

– No

Notes: It is important to note that those that did obeisance to the Famen pagoda and its interred relic were in fact offering ritual cult to the Buddha. Some may argue that the Buddha of medieval China was indeed a deified human. In the Mahāyāna scriptures, the predominant tradition that had been translated to China, the Buddha and his disciples are defined in cosmological terms, with powers and bodies that may well compare to the powers and bodies of Indian gods, even manifesting the omniscience and omnipotence characteristic of God in the Abrahamic traditions. This however would say more about the 'protestant presuppositions' that we project upon the Buddhist tradition than it would about any medieval Chinese emic understandings of the Buddha. When the Buddha died, he and his objects did turn into the pious objects of cult, though this cannot be compared to the apotheosis of a figure like Emperor Augustine. Buddhism teaches that all things are impermanent because all things arise and cease in relation with other conditions. The issue is one of ontology. The divine is the first cause, and independent thing from which all other things arise. The divine is unconditioned and permanent. The Buddha could therefore never be 'divine' or deified because all things are condition and nothing is divine/permanent.

↳ For the worship of a deceased hero:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Notes: There are dedications and donated goods such as silk, porcelain, and crafted items that were given in offering to the relic bone at Famen pagoda. However, the Famen pagoda is a commemorative monument and not a grave.

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Notes: The wording 'supreme high god' is misleading. The buddhas and bodhisattvas are considered beings with supernormal powers that go above and beyond what most untrained human beings can accomplish. The historical Buddha, Siddhartha Gotama, is believed to have attained Nirvana, at which point he gained supernormal powers (Ch. shentong 神通; Skt. abhijñā) that other non-realized beings cannot do (e.g. know one's past live, fly through the air, future sight, etc.). The historical Buddha was one of many buddhas, and the scriptures claim there will be others in the future, namely Maitreya, the future Buddha. Bodhisattvas also have supernormal powers beyond what normal beings can do. However, there is not a single supreme high god.

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– Yes

Notes: There is one example in a collection of miracle tales compiled in 664 by Daoxuan 道宣 that describes the monk Zhicong's encounter with supernormal monks in the crypt at Famen. It reads as follows: Zhicong gleefully leapt for joy, and desired to call the other monks. When he looked into the stūpa again, it was filled with monks standing with hands clasped together in prayer. they said they were all from the same monastery. A moment passed, and the light slowly subsided, descending down [further into the stūpa]. At about three chi above ground level, he could no longer see the monks. Only then did he realize that they were sacred, hidden figures. 琮大喜踊，將欲召僧。乃覩塔內，罽塞僧徒合掌而立。謂是同寺。須臾既久。光蓋漸歇，冉冉而下。去地三尺，不見群僧。方知聖隱。(T2106.407a9-12) These are not necessarily the spirits of dead humans. However, it is an example of supernormal activity in the form of humans.

Human spirits can be seen:

– Yes

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Human spirits can be physically felt:

– No

Notes: The monks mentioned in the answer above appear before the monk Zhicong, though they are non-corporeal.

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: Nonhuman spirits may be seen. The following excerpt is from a collection of miracle tales called the *Ji shenzhou sanbao gantong lu* 集神州三寶感通錄: The monk Huiman of Dacien Monastery in the capital was practicing observances at the Famen Monastery stūpa. Suddenly he saw a pair of particularly large and bright eyes beneath the painted [caisson] ceiling. He summoned practitioners and lay people [to see this], and all saw it was true. All cowered in fear, and did not again dare to look. 京師大慈恩寺僧惠滿，在塔行道。忽見綺井，覆海下一雙眼睛，光明殊大。通召道俗，同視亦然。皆懾然喪膽，更不敢重視。(T2106.407b7-10) This example speaks more broadly to the medieval Chinese belief in the supernormal. Famen monastery was a sacred place and visitors there, both pious monks and lay practitioners, certainly believed in the possibility of encountering supernatural beings or phenomena such as the one described above. Although this particular example seems to describe a fearsome presence, the supernormal phenomena at Famen was usually positive or auspicious. This however is the only record of an encounter with a nonhuman supernatural being in the collection of miracle tales.

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be physically felt:

– I don't know

Notes: There are no examples in the lore of physical contact with nonhuman supernatural beings.

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– Yes

↳ Is the cult statue visible:

– Yes

Notes: The wording 'high god' or 'supernatural being' is misleading. The buddhas and bodhisattvas are considered beings with supernatural powers that go above and beyond what most untrained human beings can accomplish. Scriptures hold that when the historical Buddha, Siddhartha Gautama, attained Nirvana, he gained supernatural powers (Ch. shentong 神通; Skt. abhijñā) that other non-realized beings cannot do (e.g. know one's past live, fly through the air, future sight, etc.). The historical Buddha was one of many buddhas, and the scriptures claim there will be others in the future, namely Maitreya, the future Buddha. Bodhisattvas also have supernatural powers beyond what normal beings can do. The Buddha and other similar supernatural beings such as bodhisattvas had cult statues dedicated to them. The cult statues of Famen are not mentioned in the records, though there certainly were statues at the monastery and in the Famen crypt. The extent to which they were offered cult is, regrettably, overshadowed by the importance of the relic bone which, along with the pagoda, was the main focus of most of the records related to Famen. There are statues still extant from the Ming dynasty onward which are kept today at the Famen monastery museum.

↳ Is the cult statue hidden:

– Yes

Notes: The wording 'high god' or 'supernatural being' is misleading. The buddhas and bodhisattvas are considered beings with supernatural powers that go above and beyond what most untrained human beings can accomplish. Scriptures hold that when the historical Buddha, Siddhartha Gautama, attained Nirvana, he gained supernatural powers (Ch. shentong 神通; Skt. abhijñā) that other non-realized beings cannot do (e.g. know one's past live, fly through the air, future sight, etc.). The historical Buddha was one of many buddhas, and the scriptures claim there will be others in the future, namely Maitreya, the future Buddha. Bodhisattvas also have supernatural powers beyond what normal beings can do. There is one example in a collection of miracle tales compiled by Daoxuan which mentions a monk called Zhicong doing obeisance and sitting in a heightened meditative state before a cult statue (or three cult statues, text ambiguous) in the Famen crypt. The story tells that he sat unperturbed until light started shining forth from the feet of these images, spiraling upwards to the rafters, where the lights came together to form a canopy above his head (T2106.407a3-9). This cult statue (or these three cult statues) were hidden away from view in the crypt. Zhicong had to get imperial approval before going to do obeisance before them.

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural monitoring of norm adherence:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect offerings:

– Yes

↳ Libations:

– No

↳ Offerings of food:

– No

↳ Animal sacrifice:

– No

↳ Human sacrifice:

– No

↳ Sacred objects:

– Yes [specify]: statues, votive pagodas, cases for the relic.

Notes: When the relic--representation for the Buddha--was carried out on religious processions, it always received gifts from pious believers and from the ruling family that patronized these events. Once returned to Famen, the relic was usually interred once more with its gifts, which include objects such as votive stupas, statues, and staves.

↳ Daily life objects:

– Yes [specify]: Silks, silverware, water vessels cash.

Notes: When the relic--representation for the Buddha--was carried out on religious processions, it always received gifts from pious believers and from the ruling family patronizing these events. Once returned to Famen, the relic was usually interred once more with its gifts, which included objects such as silks, silverware, cash and other precious objects.

↳ Other:

– Other [specify]: Self-immolation

Notes: Self-immolation is a practice with a long history in the Buddhist tradition (see James Benn 2006; 2007). There was at Famen a common practice of burning one's finger or fingers as an offering to the finger bone relic. Fazang 法藏 (643–712), an eminent Tang dyansty monk and advisor to Empress Wu Zetian, famously burnt off his thumb as an offering to the relic bone. There are records of people during the procession unable to see the relic bone until they burned their fingers. These public displays of fervent piety did not sit well with many conservatives at court, and in 819 the great literatus Han Yu 韓愈 (768–824) famously petitioned the emperor in the strongest terms to stop these processions, which he believed were barbarous foreign rites that were tearing away at the Chinese social fabric. However, Emperor Xianzong 憲宗 disagreed and exiled Han Yu for committing *Lèse-majesté*.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect proper ritual observance:

– Yes

Notes: Considering that the finger bone was equated with the Buddha himself, and that there was proscribed etiquette and rituals directed at the Buddha and his relics, we could say that the Buddha--a supernatural being insofar as he was believed to still be able to effect the world after his death--cared about proper ritual observance. There is one instance of a prophesy revealed in the early Tang required that the relic be brought out for a procession every thirty years. This requirement was, more or less, respected until the relic bone was taken out for the last time in 874.

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect performance of rituals:

– Yes

Notes: Considering that the finger bone was equated with the Buddha himself, and that there was proscribed etiquette and rituals directed at the Buddha and his relics, we could say that the Buddha--a supernatural being insofar as he was believed to still be able to effect the world after his death--cared about proper ritual observance. There is one instance of a prophesy revealed in the early Tang required that the relic be brought out for a procession every thirty years. This requirement was, more or less, respected until the relic bone was taken out for the last time in 874.

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect maintenance of the place:

– No

Notes: The pagoda was renovated multiple times during its long history. The histories of Famen Monastery record how monks usually noticed that the grounds and the pagoda at Famen were becoming old and dilapidated. It was therefore usually monks, often from neighboring monasteries, that assured the maintenance of Famen. Although supernatural beings might produce signs in reaction to the deeds of those visiting the monastery, these signs were usually not association to renovation or repairs. It would seem, at least in the case of Famen Monastery, that it was the monks that cared most for the maintenance of these sacred sites, not the supernatural beings that were there.

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect personal hygiene:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about honoring oaths:

– No

↳ Other:

–Other [specify]: No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:

– No

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: There are multiple examples of visitors at Famen encountering supernatural beings. For example, in 660 when Zhicong went to sit in quiet meditation in the crypt, he encountered a large group of spectral monks that all claimed they were originally from Famen. Later, a monk called Huiman from Daci'en Monastery in the capital did obeisance at the pagoda, at which point he noticed large eyes glaring down at him from the caisson ceiling.

Ritual and Performance

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– Yes

↳ Suicide

– No

↳ Bloodletting

– No

↳ Mutilation

– Yes

Notes: It was supposedly quite common for both practitioners and lay believers to burn off their fingers in pious devotion to the finger relic. We can not be certain how often this actually happened, but it was certainly noted by both Buddhist and secular historians, who took such fervent acts of devotion as gross aberrations of the social norm. Famously, the monk Fazang 法藏 (643-712), advisor to Wu Zetian, burned his finger at Famen Monastery as an offering to the Buddha.

Reference: Benn, James. *Burning for the Buddha: Self-immolation in Chinese Buddhism*. University of Hawai'i Press, 2007.

↳ Is self-sacrifice common and/or expect of elites:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

Notes: During renovation of the monastery, and the procession of the relic bone, offerings were expected and, especially in the case of offerings made by members of the elite, memorialized on steles.

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– Yes

Notes: The offerings made during important events were usually composed of luxury objects (i.e. silk, jewels, etc), cash, and ornate religious objects (i.e. reliquaries, votive pagodas, boxes, etc.)

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– Yes

Notes: The material offerings we have today from Famen are mostly those objects gifted to the monastery by the elite. Devotees certainly gave gifts of clothes and food to the relic and the images at the monastery. Empress Wu Zetian, for example, offered clothing of the finest silk to the relic bone when it was returned to Famen from its procession to Luoyang in 660.

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– Yes

Notes: There is a crypt with two levels at the Famen archeological site. The lowest level contains the material offerings made during the Tang. The upper crypt contained the other offering made between the Tang and the Qing dynasties, though very little remains because of looting. The Tang crypt, however, remained untouched. In the deepest cache of the pagoda crypt, they concealed the relic bone and its copies.

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Yes

↳ By all the community

– Yes

Notes: Daily ritual, lectures, and scripture readings would have been mandatory for members of the community at Famen Monastery. For bigger events, like the relic procession of the Famen finger bone relic that took place roughly every thirty years from the seventh to the ninth century, important monastic figures in the capital of Chang'an would most likely also have been asked to preside at the ceremony as well as participate in the procession.

↳ By specific individuals

– Yes [specify]: The abbot

Notes: In regular times, the abbot and other senior monks presided over the ceremonies. During special ceremonies, like the relic bone processions that took place throughout the Tang dynasty, important monks from the capital would have been expected to participate. These were imperially patronized processions, so ministers as well as members of the ruling family would also have been expected to take part in some segment of these processions which often went on for months, either participating in the procession itself or in the reception of the relic bone in either of Tang China's two capitals, Chang'an (present day Xi'an) and Luoyang. The monarch mandated the procession and therefore usually participated in the reception of the relics as well as the other rituals surrounding this ceremony.

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– Yes

Notes: The renovations to Famen usually took place to mark an event. For example, Emperor Wen of the Sui (r. 581-604) built a new pagoda in Fufeng to commemorate the history of the site. The complex later fell into disrepair until a monk by the name of Puxian 普賢 requested that the new Tang ruler, Emperor Gaozu (r. 618-626), fund its renovation. Emperor Gaozu commemorated the newly renovated monastery, giving it the name that it bears today, Famen Monastery. These were lavish ceremonies with all the pomp and pageantry expected of an imperial ceremony. Buddhist monastics, as well as commoners and the elite participated in these performances. The rituals were usually accompanied by gifts of cash and other goods to the monastery.

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– I don't know

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

Notes: Famen was reconstructed many times from its early history until the modern era. The last time it was reconstructed in pre-modern Chinese history was during the Ming dynasty in 1579. The entire complex was renovated in 1988.

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– No

Notes: Monastics certainly took care, to a certain degree, of the maintenance. However, larger renovation projects would have been done by local craftsmen, or artisan from the capital.

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: No

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– optional (common)

Notes: Famen was an important lieu of cult in Tang dynasty China. It was best known for the relic bone of the Buddha that it kept in the crypt to the Famen pagoda. Its proximity to the capital of Chang'an allowed for easy access to Famen for those monks that wanted to come do obeisance before the pagoda. Famously, the monk Fazang 法藏 (643-712) went to Famen and burned his finger as an offering to the Buddha.

↳ Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:

– No

↳ Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:

– No

↳ Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Are festivals present:

– Yes

↳ Frequency of festivals

– specify: Finger bone procession

Notes: After the discovery of an ancient finger bone at Famen in 630, there were finger bone processions roughly every thirty years until the mid ninth century. These were imperially mandated processions that invited people from all walks of life to participate: commoners, monastics, lay believers, ministers and even members of the ruling family. The cult to the relic bone continued in the tenth century, but the relic processions were terminated.

↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):

– All members

↳ Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:

– No

↳ On average, how many participants gather at this place:

– number: Uncertain

Notes: In Buddhist and secular histories, they describe huge gatherings of people. Famen was near the capital of Chang'an, the most populated urban center in Tang dynasty China. However, I cannot say for certain how many people participated in the relic procession.

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s):

– I don't know

Notes: It was common practice to hold a vegetarian feast, also translated meagre feast, for the community. However, there is no mention of these feast in the case of Famen and the relic procession. It is safe to assume that there were, though I cannot say for certain.

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– Yes

↳ Divination by examination of the exta:

Animals remains, internal organs, answer this question and subsequent question once for each species

– No

↳ Divination through human communication:

– No

↳ Divination through animal-behavior:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Divination through non-living material:

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: Regarding Famen in premodern China, there is no information about formal divination practices. However, the many services that monastics provided for the state included divination and the interpretation of signs. I do not have any examples specific to Famen, though divination practices were almost certainly present at the monastery. At present day Famen you can get your fortune read using lottery poetry (qiuqian 求籤), a practice found everywhere in East Asia. It consists of a container with bamboo sticks that all have different numbers scrawled on their surface. After doing obeisance before the Buddha, one can shake the container until a viable answer (two rounded bamboo sticks facing up) fall out onto the ground. This, however, was probably not practiced in early Buddhist monasteries where divination was usually associated to dream interpretation and the interpretation of auspicious--or inauspicious--signs.

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: None

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– Yes

↳ Incubation

– No

↳ Healing magic

– No

↳ Cleansing

– I don't know

↳ Offerings of models of body parts:

– No

Notes: In practices dedicated to the finger bone, some people, commoners and practitioners, were known to burn off their fingers in the hope of gaining the Buddha's grace and healing an ailment or to repent.

↳ Expiation

– Yes

Notes: The healing practices related to Famen all involve the relic bone. As a synecdochical object embodying the Buddha's "presence" and power, the relic bone was considered to have apotropaic and therapeutic powers. The records of Famen include many stories of blind people regaining their sight in the presence of the relic. In another narrative, a non-believer is

driven mad after burning a Buddhist image. It was only after he burned off finger in the presence of the relic that he regained his wits. Repentance before the relic, not only in the form of self-immolation, was considered to be an effective therapeutic practice.

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Relic proximity

Notes: On two occasions, emperors brought the relic to the palace in the hopes of healing their ailments. In 660 after emperor Gaozu suffered a stroke--one of many--he had the relic brought to the palace. Unfortunately it did not have the desired effect and his health continued to deteriorate. In 704, his wife Wu Zhao, then known as Empress Wu Zetian (r. 690-705), received the relic at the palace. She was ill and was hoping to draw on its therapeutic powers. She passed away the next year in 705.

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Notes: The largest ritual that took place at Famen was the procession of its most precious sacred object: the finger bone of the Buddha. In premodern China, the cult of the finger bone relic was an important imperially mandated ceremony. Even in the Republic of China, it is still honored and venerated through government sanctioned "processions". In 2002 it was brought to the Taiwan University stadium in Taipei and in 2004 it visited Hong Kong. In 2017, thirty years after the relic was rediscovered, the relic was celebrated in the city of Baoji, Shaanxi.

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Notes: As it was in many other monasteries, the daily comings and goings of the monks at Famen Monastery were punctuated by ritual activities such as sutra reading, offerings to the images, etc.

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

–specify: Unknown

Notes: These were large-scale imperially mandated processions that took place near the capital of Chang'an. The relic was brought to the palace in Chang'an as well as the eastern capital of Luoyang. All were allowed to attend the procession. It is difficult to estimate how many people might have participated, but considering that commoners, practitioners, and the elite were in attendance, the number of participants was certainly quite high.

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

–specify: Relic procession

Notes: The most important ritual out of Famen was the procession dedicated to the Buddha's finger bone. After the relic was unearthed in 630 at Famen, it was brought out for large-scale religious processions roughly every thirty years (660; 704; 760; 790; 819).

- ↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are there synchronic practices:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:
 - No

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

- ↳ Present full time
 - Yes

Notes: The abbot, rectors, senior monks, and junior monks all live at the monastery full-time.

- ↳ Present part time
 - Yes

Notes: It was common practice for monks to travel, study, and teach at different monasteries. Therefore, there were always monastic specialists staying as guests at Famen Monastery.

- ↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:
 - Yes

Notes: Famen Monastery was for men only. There were nunneries near Famen, and the religious specialists residing in the nunneries of China were exclusively female.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– No

Notes: In the early days of Buddhism's transmission to China, the religious specialists were all foreigners from Central and Southern Asia. By the Tang dynasty, Buddhism had pretty well been naturalized, and many of the religious specialists were from the region.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– No

Notes: As a rule, monastics were not of a specific class. However, the majority of the well known religious specialists mentioned in the biographies were from wealthy or well-educated families with associations to the higher strata of society. That being said, there are examples of monastics that came from poorer backgrounds and wealth or class was not a condition for joining the fold.

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– No

Notes: Monastics often stayed at a monastery under the tutelage of one religious specialist or another. It was common practice in premodern China for monks and nuns to travel across the country to study under other masters in other monasteries. Even the title of abbot was not a lifetime commitment, unless the abbot wished to stay.

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– Yes

Notes: The abbot and other higher ranking masters at the monastery would have had better lodgings, to a certain degree separate from the other members of the community.

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Yes

Notes: The monastery had living quarters for its monks and for its visiting monastics.

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Yes

Notes: Master-disciple relations usually took place within the context of the monastic compound. A monastery such as Famen would also have provided a curriculum covering subjects relevant to the masters in place at the time (e.g. contemplative practice, monastic regulation, etc.)

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Notes: Broadly speaking, the maintenance of all monasteries was the responsibility of community officials (sengguan 僧官), headed by the Buddhist Rector (sengzheng 僧正). The Rector, usually a Buddhist master with clout among the elite, was appointed by the imperial family and was responsible for a parallel administrative branch, beholden to the state, that was responsible for the Buddhist religious communities of China. That being said, monastic communities were still relatively independent, though for larger renovations or big construction projects, they usually had to go through the Buddhist Rector and his subordinates, or memorialize the emperor themselves.

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Yes

Reference: Antonino, Forte. "Daisōjō: Grand Recteur Du Samgha". In *Hōbōgirin: Dictionnaire Encyclopédique Du Bouddhisme D'après Les Sources Chinoises Et Japonaises*, Vol. 7. Maison Franco-Japonaise, 2003. p.1043-1070

↳ Is a bureaucracy present permanently:

– Yes

Notes: There was a formal hierarchy within every monastery, usually headed by an abbot (sengzhu 僧主). The monastery had its treasurer, its chief of kitchen affairs, and other such positions that were relevant for the smooth running of day to day monastic life. They were, however, all beholden to the state and to administrator monks appointed by the staff that ran the office of religious Buddhist affairs. From the outset, these administrator monks, headed by the Rector (sengzhen 僧正) and the Registrar (senglū 僧錄), were figures chosen by the state to represent the interests of the Buddhist religious communities and to ensure that these communities respected state regulations, usually related to taxation and conversion rates.

↳ Is a bureaucracy present on a temporary or seasonal basis:

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Yes

↳ Is this control the primary supporting income of this place:

– Yes

↳ Does this place lease out land:

– I don't know

Notes: At different times in Chinese history, monasteries were known to make extra income by leasing land to commoners so that they may till and work it. This was probably the case in Famen, though it is not mentioned anywhere in the sources.

Does this place lease out tools:

– I don't know

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– I don't know

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– Yes

Notes: Monastery libraries usually contained all kinds of texts. For example, the cache of texts discovered in Dunhuang revealed that the monastic libraries of that important religious center contained not only Buddhist texts, but also Confucian, Daoist, historical, and administrative documents. We do not know anything about the library at Famen, though one has to assume that they stored records and administrative documents therein.

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– Field doesn't know

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